

plastic tube cage was placed over the potted plants and pushed into the soil. A third hill of rice, which represented sprayed plants and paddy water, was likewise caged in each plot after spraying. Ten second-instar larvae were introduced into each cage and mortality was determined 48 hours later by opening the larval cases.

The results showed that caseworm larvae were controlled readily with

insecticides applied at 0.75 kg a.i./ha (see table). All chemicals tested significantly reduced plant damage and caused high larval mortality compared with the untreated check. MIPC and triazophos were the most toxic and MTMC the least toxic of the chemicals tested. Most insecticides were highly effective when applied to either plants or paddy water. However, when only plants were sprayed, MTMC and endosulfan killed

significantly fewer larvae than most of the other insecticides. When only the paddy water was sprayed, MTMC appeared to be the least effective.

The results indicate that the rice caseworm can be controlled effectively with one insecticide application after transplanting because this insect is a pest only during the tillering stage. Future trials should test insecticides at lower dosages. ■

Rice grasshopper outbreak in West Bengal, India

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The rice grasshopper *Hieroglyphus banian* (Fabricius) is a minor insect pest of wetland rice. Unclean cultivation and weed growth in and around rice fields usually favor its occurrence.

In October 1980 the grasshopper attacked about 3,000 ha of wetland rice in Midnapore, West Bengal. It appears that the well-distributed rainfall in the months preceding the infestation promoted the growth of weeds, which are alternate hosts of the grasshopper. After the initial proliferation, the insect migrated to rice.

During the attack the rice was mainly in the boot-leaf and flowering stages. The varieties that suffered most were Kakhuria, Bombai Mugi, Bhutia, Nona, and Sundarsail — all tall, photoperiod-

Grasshopper damaging the boot leaf and emerging panicle in West Bengal, India.

sensitive indica varieties that mature in about 160 days. However, the rice variety Jaya was also attacked.

The insect fed on the foliage, flag

leaves, and the leaf sheaths on the upper part of the rice plant. As a result the emerging inflorescence was exposed (see photo) and became sterile. ■

Gryon nixon Masner (Hymenoptera: Scelionidae): a new egg parasite of *Leptocorisa oratorius* in the Philippines

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Two egg parasites of the rice bug *Leptocorisa oratorius* (= *L. acuta* in the reports of Uichanco 1921, 1949; Otanes and Sison 1941) have been recorded in the Philippines: 1) *Ooencyrtus malayensis* Ferriere (Encyrtidae) and 2) *Teleno-*

mus comperei Crawford (Scelionidae). In a 1978-79 field trial at IRRI to compare the natural enemy abundance in weekly and biannual cropping patterns without insecticide, an egg parasite of *L. oratorius* was found new to the Philippines.

The study used rice cultivars IR36 and IR1917 from October 1978 to January 1979. Potted mature plants laden with 1-day-old eggs of *L. oratorius* from a greenhouse colony were placed in the field at weekly intervals from flowering to hard dough stages of the field crop.

Parasitization of rice bug eggs by *Gryon nixon* Masner obtained by exposing potted plants laden with *Leptocorisa oratorius* eggs in a portion of a weekly-cropped area planted the same week as biannual fields of IR36 and IR1917 without insecticide. IRRI. 1978-79.

Cropping system	Cultivar	Eggs exposed (no.)	Parasitized eggs (no.)	Parasitization (%)
Weekly	IR36	589	173	29
Biannual	IR36	288	52	18
Weekly	IR1917	147	23	16
Biannual	IR1917	213	9	4